

Rapid Rise in Light Pollution Estimated by NOIRLab's Citizen-Science Program

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As astronomers, we are inherently concerned about light pollution affecting our research as well as the environment around us, our health, and our level of energy consumption.

The artificial glow of the night sky is a form of light pollution; its global change over time is not well known. Developments in lighting technology complicate any measurement because of changes in lighting practice and emission spectra.

NOIRLab has had an international citizen-science campaign running for the last 17 years, [Globe at Night](#). GLOBE at Night invites people from around the world to compare the campaign's monthly featured constellation with the charts shown in its app. The charts represent different limiting stellar magnitudes. Hence charts with fainter magnitudes represent less light-polluted skies because more stars are seen.

In a recent paper by Kyba et al. (2023), we investigated the change in global sky brightness from 2011 to 2022 using 51,351 GLOBE at Night citizen-scientist observations

of naked-eye stellar visibility (Figure 1). The number of visible stars decreased by an amount that can be explained by an increase in sky brightness of 9.6% worldwide per year (10.4% in North America) in the human-eye visible band (Figure 2). This is equivalent to doubling the sky brightness every eight years! This increase is faster than emissions changes indicated by satellite observations (2%). This is mainly because the satellites are not sensitive to the wavelengths (shorter than 500 nm) at which white LEDs (primarily from cities) peak or to light emitted horizontally. In addition, blue light is more effectively scattered in the atmosphere than other colors. These two effects give a possible reason for the lower estimate from orbital-based light pollution measurements versus the ground-based estimates studied by Kyba et al.

We draw two conclusions from these results. First, the naked-eye visibility of stars is deteriorating rapidly despite (or perhaps because of) the introduction of LEDs in outdoor lighting applications. Existing lighting policies are not preventing increases in skyglow, at least on continental and global scales. Second, the use of

Figure 1: The light pollution of Tucson, Arizona, can be seen in the backdrop of this photo of Kitt Peak National Observatory, with the Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope featured prominently. In addition to being an aesthetic blight, light pollution poses one of the greatest risks to astronomical research at Kitt Peak, drowning out the natural starlight and the light from distant asteroids, comets, galaxies, quasars, and other objects in the night sky.
Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/B. Tafreshi

Figure 2. The map of the USA shows colored dots ranging from dark brown to yellow to white. The darker the dot, the darker the sky. The brighter the dot, the brighter the sky. In 2020, with the help of citizen scientists worldwide, the Globe at Night citizen science campaign collected 29,404 total observations. This data was among the data in the Kyba et al 2023 Science article. To explore this year's Globe at Night map, visit globeatnight.org/map/?year=2020. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/Globe at Night

Figure 3: Relationship between naked-eye limiting magnitude estimated by Globe at Night participants and the modeled artificial brightness of the night sky in 2014. "Sky brightness factor" (SBF) is the ratio of total radiance to natural sky radiance, so a factor of 1 here means the sky is 10 times brighter than starlight. The relationship is shown for two separate years (green, blue) and all years together (gray). Smaller naked-eye limiting magnitude (NELM) values mean a brighter sky. The fit lines are calculated only for $\log_{10}(\text{SBF}) > 0.5$, which corresponds to about 3 times brighter than starlight. Credit: Kyba et al. 2023

naked-eye observations by citizen-scientists provides complementary information to datasets from satellites.

Skyglow from light pollution can be reduced. The [DarkSky strategies for cutting light pollution](#) are straightforward: use outdoor lighting only when, where, and how it is needed; minimize blue light content; and use fully shielded fixtures. As the results from the Kyba et al. study indicate, more effort is

needed to put these recommendations into ordinances, bylaws, and other regulations to slow down and hopefully reverse the degradation of our shared night sky.

Reference

Kyba, C. C. M., Altıntaş, Y. Ö., Walker, C. E., Newhouse, M. 2023, *Sci*, 379(6629), 265. doi.org/10.1126/science.abq778

Figure 4: The fit residuals (observed minus expected) for naked-eye limiting magnitude are shown with (a) the standard World Atlas prediction and (b) the Atlas adjusted for an annual exponential growth of 9.60% per year. Larger values mean observers reported more stars than expected. Note that data points before 2014 include a larger number of observations than those after 2014. Error bars show the standard error. Credit: Kyba et al. 2023